

Table 2. Referrals to a psychologist in the last 6 months.

Referrals	AHPs N=36 N (%)	Clinicians N=94 N (%)	Total N=130 N (%)
Actual			
None (no service)	8 (22.2)	31 (33.0)	39 (30.0)
None (no requirement)	4 (11.1)	10 (10.6)	14 (10.8)
1-4	15 (41.7)	33 (35.1)	48 (36.9)
5-10	8 (22.2)	16 (17.0)	24 (18.5)
10-15	1 (2.8)	1 (1.1)	2 (1.5)
15+	0	3 (3.2)	3 (2.3)
Desirable			
None	1 (2.8)	5 (5.3)	6 (4.6)
1-4	4 (11.1)	21 (22.3)	25 (19.2)
5-10	9 (25.0)	20 (21.3)	29 (22.3)
10-15	8 (22.2)	14 (14.9)	22 (16.9)
15+	13 (36.1)	26 (27.7)	39 (30.0)
Don't know	1 (2.8)	8 (8.5)	9 (6.9)
Referrals	London and the South N=51	Midlands and the North N=79	Total N=130 N (%)
Actual			
None (no service)	14 (27.5)	25 (31.6)	39 (30.0)
None (no requirement)	3 (5.9)	11 (13.9)	14 (10.8)
1-4	22 (43.1)	26 (32.9)	48 (36.9)
5-10	9 (17.6)	15 (19.0)	24 (18.5)
10-15	1 (2.0)	1 (1.3)	2 (1.5)
15+	2 (3.9)	1 (1.3)	3 (2.3)
Desirable			
None	2 (3.9)	4 (5.1)	6 (4.6)
1-4	6 (11.8)	19 (24.1)	25 (19.2)
5-10	10 (19.6)	19 (24.1)	29 (22.3)
10-15	8 (15.7)	14 (17.7)	22 (16.9)
15+	19 (37.3)	20 (25.3)	39 (30.0)
Don't know	6 (11.8)	3 (3.8)	9 (6.9)